

Mass and ^{13}C Nmr Spectral Studies of some 1,5-Di- and 1,3,5-Trisubstituted Fluorine-containing Hydantoins

KRISHNA C. JOSHI*, VIJAI N. PATHAK and MAHENDRA K. GOYAL

Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 10 November 1988, accepted 26 June 1989

The mass spectral decomposition modes of various hydantoin derivatives containing C-5 fluoroaryl, N-aryl, N-3 dialkylaminomethyl, N-3 chloroacetyl and N-3 dialkylaminoacetyl substituents have been investigated. ^{13}C nmr spectral studies of some of the representative compounds have also been discussed.

RECENTLY, the chemistry and biological activity of hydantoins and allied derivatives aroused great interest due to the diverse type of biological activities associated with hydantoin moiety¹ viz., lowering of blood sugar level in mammals², antiarrhythmic³, antitubercular³, anti-inflammatory⁴, antitumor⁵ and anticonvulsant⁶ activities. We have therefore undertaken a comprehensive programme for developing new biologically active fluorine-containing hydantoins and allied derivatives and have already reported the synthesis, anticonvulsant and analgesic activities of a number of new fluorine-containing 1,5-disubstituted-hydantoins⁷, Mannich bases derived from 1,5-disubstituted-hydantoins and 3-dialkylaminoacetyl-1,5-diarylhydantoins⁸. However, a perusal of literature revealed that there has been only one report concerning the mass spectral studies of hydantoins⁴ and no reference is available for ^{13}C nmr spectral studies. Keeping this in view, we now report on mass spectral studies of 1,5-disubstituted-hydantoins of type (1a-g, 1,3,5-trisubstituted-hydantoins of types 2a-d and 3a-d); and ^{13}C nmr spectral studies of some representative com-

pounds from types 1, 2 and 3 (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

TABLE 1 - RELATIVE ABUNDANCE OF PRINCIPAL FRAGMENTS* FOR 1,5-DISUBSTITUTED-HYDANTOINS (I)

Compd. no.	Ar	ϕ	M^+	$M+1$	$M+2$	M^+-71	M^+-72	$\text{C}\equiv\text{N}-\phi]^+$	$\phi]^+$	CH^+-N^+
			I	(a)	(b)	II	II'	IV	V	IV
1a	4-F	C_6H_5	270 (100)	-	-	199 (73)	198 (62)	103 (9)	77 (44)	104 (9)
1b	2Cl, 4-F	C_6H_5	304 (43)	305 (6)	306 (14)	233 (67)	232 (47)	103 (10)	77 (100)	104 (23)
1c	3Cl, 4-F	C_6H_5	304 (100)	305 (16)	306 (32)	233 (90)	232 (54)	103 (17)	77 (68)	104 (23)
1d	2F, 5- CH_3	C_6H_5	284 (99)	285 (41)	-	213 (99)	212 (100)	103 (10)	77 (62)	104 (11)
1e	4F, 3- CH_3	C_6H_5	284 (100)	285 (22)	-	213 (86)	212 (63)	103 (8)	77 (65)	104 (18)
1f	4-F	4-Cl- C_6H_4	304 (100)	305 (17)	306 (32)	233 (87)	232 (63)	137 (11)	111 (36)	138 (10)
1g	3Cl, 4-F	4- CH_3 - C_6H_4	318 (100)	319 (15)	320 (33)	247 (95)	246 (51)	117 (12)	91 (50)	118 (15)

*Figure in parenthesis indicate abundance of the ion.

Results and Discussion

Mass spectral studies: Molecular ions of the hydantoins (1a-g) under electron impact eliminate NHCO and CO moieties simultaneously instead of step-wise fragmentation to give rise to (II), which in turn, eliminates hydrogen radical and gives III; an abundance peak at m/z 198 (1a); 232 (1b-c, 1f); 212 (1d-e, and 246 (1g) respectively (Table 1). Further elimination of C-5 fluoroaryl moiety is preferred over N-3 aryl moiety and subsequently fragmentation proceeds via IV and V leading to a stable V Ar^+ moiety (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

Further, base peak is the molecular ion peak in compounds 1a, 1c, 1e-g while in case of 1b and 1d, it is observed at m/z 77 and 212 respectively. In addition to these peaks, the molecular ions corresponding to 1b, 1c, 1f and 1g showed prominent isotopic peaks corresponding to the presence of one chlorine atom

The Mannich bases (2a-c) exhibit M^+ ion peaks at m/z 383, 403 and 383 corresponding to their molecular masses. Base peak in these compounds (2a-c) invariably has been observed at m/z 100, corresponding to morpholinomethylene group and in 2d at m/z 86, corresponding to diethylaminomethylene group. It is interesting to note that the loss of CH_2R group, in all these Mannich bases (2a-d), is accompanied by simultaneous migration of β -hydrogen via McLafferty rearrangement (Scheme 4).

Scheme 3

After loss of a proton from VII, further fragmentation pattern is similar to those of hydantoins as presented in Scheme 2 and detail mass spectral data of these compounds are recorded in Table 2.

Scheme 4

TABLE 2—RELATIVE ABUNDANCE OF PRINCIPAL FRAGMENTS* FOR 1,3,5-TRISUBSTITUTED HYDANTOINS (2 AND 3)

Compd. no.	Ar	φ	M^+ VII	$M+1$ (a)	$M+2$ (b)	VIII	II	III	V
2a	4-F, 3- CH_3	C_6H_5	383 (24)	—	—	284 (9)	—	—	77 (6)
2b	2Cl, 4-F	C_6H_5	403 (27)	404 (6)	405 (9)	304 (9)	233 (12)	232 (10)	77 (7)
2c	2F, 5- CH_3	C_6H_5	383 (29)	—	—	284 (22)	—	—	77 (19)
2d	2Cl, 4-F	C_6H_5	389 (00)	—	—	304 (7)	233 (56)	232 (64)	77 (90)
3a	4-F	C_6H_5	346 (14)	347 (22)	—	270 (100)	199 (74)	198 (59)	77 (16)
3b	4-F	4- CH_3 - C_6H_4	360 (4)	—	—	284 (31)	213 (57)	212 (100)	91 (100)
3c	4-F	4-Cl- C_6H_4	381 (3)	382 (6)	—	305 (37)	233 (59)	232 (81)	111 (57)
3d	4-F	C_6H_5	354 (5)	—	—	270 (91)	199 (100)	198 (97)	77 (72)

*Figure in parenthesis indicate nature of the ion.

The molecular ion peaks of compounds 3a-c are observed at m/z 346, 360 and 381, and base peak at m/z 270, 212 and 231, respectively. Loss of COCH_2Cl moiety in all these compounds (3a-c) is accompanied by McLafferty rearrangement (Scheme 4).

Mass spectral fragmentation pattern of compound 3d is similar to other hydantoin and elimination of $\text{COCH}=\text{NC}_2\text{H}_5$ moiety, accompanied by McLafferty rearrangement, gives rise to abundant peak at m/z 270.

¹³C nmr spectral studies: ¹³C nmr spectral studies of five representative compounds, 5-(4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenylhydantoin (1a), 5-(4-fluoro-3-methylphenyl)-1-phenylhydantoin (1e), 5-(4-fluoro-3-methylphenyl)-3-morpholinomethyl-1-phenylhydantoin (2a), 5-(2-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-3-morpholinomethyl-1-phenylhydantoin (2b) and 3-chloroacetyl-5-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)-1-phenylhydantoin (3e) have been studied. Detailed ¹³C nmr data of these compounds are recorded in Table 3.

δ 157.37-155.98 and 155.26-152.64 ppm respectively. The tertiary methyl group (C-5, d) exhibits resonance signals at δ 64.83-61.20 ppm. The methyl group (CH_3 , q) of hydantoin 1e and 2a shows a resonance signal at δ 14.59 ppm.

Hydantoin of type 2a and 2b show a new resonance signal in the region δ 60.48-59.07 ppm due to methylene group flanked by tertiary nitrogen on either side. In addition to this, additional resonance signals have been observed at δ 66.83-66.77 ppm due to $\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2$ and at δ 50.88 ppm due to $\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2$ carbons. Compound 3e shows a new carbonyl resonance signal at δ 163.71 ppm. The signal at δ 64.05 ppm is associated due to methylene (CH_2 , t) group of this hydantoin. All these ¹³C nmr shift assignments are based on off resonance spectral studies and/or with comparative spectral studies with authentic groups⁶.

Experimental

Syntheses of 1,5-di- and 1,3,5-trisubstituted-hydantoin has been reported earlier by us⁶.

TABLE 3 - ¹³C NMR SPECTRAL DATA FOR 1,5-DI- AND 1,3,5-TRISUBSTITUTED-HYDANTOINS* IN CDCl_3 (δ IN PPM FROM SiMe_4)

Carbon atom	2a	1e	2a	2b	3e
C-2	171.12 (s)	171.22 (s)	171.25 (s)	170.38 (s)	170.29 (s)
C-4	163.31 (s)	166.92 (s)	167.21 (s)	168.28 (s)	170.87 (s)
C-5	64.67 (d)	64.83 (d)	63.82 (d)	61.20 (d)	62.53 (d)
C-1'	136.43 (s)	144.84 (s)	136.30 (s)	135.71 (s)	136.52 (s)
C-2'	129.21 (d)	136.52 (d)	130.15 (d)	129.95 (s)	130.70 (d)
C-3'	116.60 (d)	116.20 (s)	116.68 (s)	116.88 (d)	116.81 (s)
C-4'	157.37 (s)	156.01 (s)	156.27 (s)	157.11 (s)	155.98 (s)
C-5'	115.60 (d)	115.19 (d)	115.65 (d)	115.81 (d)	115.16 (d)
C-6'	129.01 (d)	129.01 (d)	129.24 (d)	128.33 (d)	130.21 (d)
C-1''	155.01 (d)	155.04 (s)	155.33 (s)	155.26 (s)	152.64 (s)
C-2''	120.70 (d)	121.41 (d)	120.86 (d)	119.11 (d)	121.31 (d)
C-3''	124.68 (d)	124.58 (d)	125.06 (d)	121.12 (d)	124.81 (d)
C-4''	128.63 (d)	126.10 (d)	129.29 (d)	125.29 (d)	126.72 (d)
C-5''	129.0 (d)	129.95 (d)	129.89 (d)	129.27 (d)	130.53 (d)
C-6''	120.27 (d)	120.57 (d)	120.50 (d)	118.85 (d)	120.60 (d)
CH_3	-	14.59 (q)	14.59 (q)	-	-
NCH_2N	-	-	60.48 (t)	59.07 (t)	-
$\text{N}(\text{CH}_2)_2$	-	-	66.77 (t)	66.83 (t)	-
$\text{O}(\text{CH}_2)_2$	-	-	50.88 (t)	50.88 (t)	-
CO	-	-	-	-	163.71 (s)
CH_2	-	-	-	-	64.05 (t)

*In CDCl_3 (δ in ppm from SiMe_4)

Two carbonyl groups of these hydantoin (C-2 and C-4, s) are observed in the range δ 171.25-166.92 ppm region. The absorption peak in the downfield region has been assigned to a $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group of the hydantoin at position-2 while a second in the up-field region is associated due to the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ group at position-4. All these hydantoin show characteristic aromatic carbon signals of ¹³C nmr in the region δ 157.37-115.16 ppm region. The carbon atoms attached to fluorine (C-4') and nitrogen (C-1') have been observed in the region

Mass spectra were obtained by using Karatos MS-30 and MS-50 mass spectrometers at the Institut für Organische Chemie und Biochemie der Universität Bonn, West Germany. The samples were recorded at an ionisation chamber temperature of 190° and operating at 70 eV, and ¹³C nmr spectra (CDCl_3) using Bruker HX-90 spectrometer.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. Dr. Dieter Enders, Institut für Organische Chemie und

Biochemie der Universität Bonn, West Germany for generous permission to record the spectra and to Dr. Arif H. Shah for help offered for recording spectra. The financial assistances from U.G.C. and C.S.I.R., New Delhi are gratefully acknowledged

References

1. M I HUSAIN and M. NASIR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 56, 177; H. T. HAVERA and W. G STRYCKER, US Pat. 3 835 151/1973 (*Chem. Abstr.*, 1973, 61, 152224); J. P. GUPTA and A. S. GUPTA, *Indian J Chem., Sect. B*, 1979, 16, 71; K. E. SCHULTE and W. V. VON, *Eur. J. Med. Chem. Chim. Ther.*, 1978, 13, 25; T. R. RODGERS, M P LAMONTAGNE, A MARKOVIC and A B ASH, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1977, 20, 591; B. DZIEDZIC, A. SZADOWSKA and A. RAMINSKA, *Acta Pol. Pharm*, 1978, 35 423.
2. K. C JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and M. K. GOYAL, *J. Heterocycl. Chem.*, 1981, 18, 1651.
3. K. C. JOSHI, V. N. PATHAK and M. K. GOYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1985, 62, 904.
4. R. A. CORRAL and O. O. ORAZI, *Org. Mass Spectrom.*, 1971, 5, 551.
5. R. M. SILVERSTEIN and G. C. BASSLER, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1981, p. 249.